

Symbolic Pricing Policies for Attended Home Delivery - the Case of an Online Retailer

Miguel Lunet
miguel.lunet@inesctec.pt
INESC TEC
Porto, Portugal

Fábio Neves-Moreira
fabio.s.moreira@inesctec.pt
Faculty of Economics of University of Porto
Porto, Portugal
INESC TEC
Porto, Portugal

Daniela Fernandes
daniela.fernandes@inesctec.pt
INESC TEC
Porto, Portugal

Pedro Amorim
pamorim@fe.up.pt
Faculty of Engineering of University of Porto
Porto, Portugal
INESC TEC
Porto, Portugal

ABSTRACT

To get products delivered, clients and retailers agree on a delivery time window. We collaborated with an online retailer to develop a real-world application aimed at dynamically determining the delivery fee for each time window while ensuring the explainability of the pricing policy. This sequential decision-making problem arises as new customers continuously arrive. The objective is to maximize the final profit, given by the sum of baskets and delivery fees, discounted by the transportation and fleet costs. As multiple customers share the same delivery route, the costs are distributed among them, complicating the calculation of the marginal cost of each customer. Our study employs Genetic Programming (GP) to create explainable and easy-to-compute pricing policies to determine the delivery fees. These policies, expressed as mathematical formulas, rank price panels – combinations of time slots and corresponding fees – to identify optimal prices for each customer. The inputs to the GP algorithm capture the current state of the system, including factors such as capacity, customer location, and basket value. The resulting expressions offer operational managers a transparent pricing policy that allows them to maximize total profit.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Applied computing** → **Transportation**; **Online shopping**; • **Computing methodologies** → **Planning under uncertainty**; **Markov decision processes**; **Genetic programming**.

KEYWORDS

attended home delivery, dynamic pricing, sequential decision-making, genetic programming, vehicle routing, explainable artificial intelligence

ACM Reference Format:

Miguel Lunet, Daniela Fernandes, Fábio Neves-Moreira, and Pedro Amorim. 2025. Symbolic Pricing Policies for Attended Home Delivery - the Case of an Online Retailer. In *Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference*

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© 2025 Copyright held by the owner/author(s).
ACM ISBN 979-8-4007-1465-8/2025/07
<https://doi.org/10.1145/3712256.3726361>

(*GECCO '25*), July 14–18, 2025, Málaga, Spain. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 9 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3712256.3726361>

1 INTRODUCTION

In Attended Home Delivery (AHD), clients and retailers must agree on a time window for delivery. Upon checkout, the customer is presented with a price panel showing fees associated with each available time slot. Based on individual preferences, the customer decides whether to choose a slot and commit to the respective delivery fee or walk away without making a purchase. The presented price panel influences the time slot choice and, consequently, impacts the company's profit.

Due to demand and delivery cost estimations, defining the best price panel to nudge customer behavior and increase profitability represents a significant problem. The challenge in calculating the marginal delivery cost for each customer lies in the fact that these costs cannot be computed in isolation. When multiple customers are served on the same route, delivery costs are shared among them. Furthermore, serving an earlier customer may lead to displacement costs, reflecting the potential lost revenue if a later customer is unable to book due to the lack of logistics capacity. An inefficient pricing strategy can lead to reduced profits in several ways: by increasing transportation costs due to sparse routes, requiring a larger fleet to handle demand concentrated in the most popular time slots, and losing valuable customers by offering myopic incentives.

Traditional pricing approaches include the utilization of a static panel or two-tier pricing schemes, in which customers are discriminated based on basket value or location. Dynamic methods are also deeply studied in literature [8][9][15][19][18], with Approximate Dynamic Programming (ADP) being the most frequent approach to deal with the “curse of dimensionality” inherent to the problem. In real-world applications, retailers face challenges often overlooked by the research community, such as multi-period delivery options and driver shift scheduling. Customers can select delivery across several days, influenced by panel pricing, requiring an integrated approach. Retailer operations and route planning must align with driver shifts, where costs are calculated per shift and tied to booking cutoff times to ensure adequate picking and loading preparation.

The online retailer we collaborate with employs a three-day price panel system and requires driver shift considerations for accurate

delivery cost calculation. For a good customer shopping experience, it is crucial to swiftly define the price panel presented to customers. Thus, the decision-making process should be rapid and not rely on intensive computations. Additionally, the company prefers a transparent approach, avoiding black-box models to maintain the explainability of the pricing policy for operational managers.

We utilize Genetic Programming (GP) [11] within a sequential decision-making framework [14] to achieve the aforementioned objectives. The features input into the GP algorithm include data regarding the current system state. The evolutionary algorithm combines these features into a mathematical expression. The derived expression is used to calculate the score of each price panel, with the highest-scored panel being shown to the customer. The use of easily interpretable terminals and operators results in a pricing policy that is explainable by design. Furthermore, we involved operational managers in the feature selection process to ensure the pricing policy outcome is both understandable and applicable within the company’s operational context. The developed work highlights the potential of Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) in the use case of our online retail partner.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we provide context regarding approaches for similar problems discussed in the literature. Section 3 formulates the problem as a Markov Decision Process (MDP) and explains the customer choice model. Section 4 details the panel selection framework. Section 5 elaborates on the evolutionary algorithm used to derive symbolic expressions as decision policies. In Section 6, we present the numerical experiments comparing various pricing policies over two business settings with respect to achieved profit and explainability. Finally, Section 7 presents the conclusions and future research directions that emerged from this work.

2 RELATED WORK

Dynamic pricing allows retailers to tailor customer-specific delivery fees or other incentives associated with different service options, stimulating efficient fulfillment operations and maximizing revenue [1]. Even simple incentive schemes with incentives to only a few time slots can reduce delivery costs [3]. In many cases, compared to a static price policy, dynamic pricing is a win-win situation, both for the company and for the customer [4].

Typically, grocery delivery requires direct interaction with the customer at the time of delivery, a model known as AHD. In [12], the authors examine how some companies adapted their business models to address the logistical complexity of scheduling delivery time slots with customers. These companies introduced an innovative solution by installing refrigerators with security locks at customers’ premises free of charge, allowing deliveries to occur at any time of day. This approach offered greater convenience for customers and reduced delivery costs by extending the delivery window. However, the high upfront investment in these refrigerators ultimately proved unsustainable, highlighting the critical importance of improving customer-slot allocation strategies.

It is possible to develop a customized price panel for each region, zip code, customer type, or even for each individual customer. In slots context, the decisions can be regarding the slots to show (slotting) and the delivery fee in each slot (pricing). An intimate

understanding of vehicle routing is a prerequisite for appropriately assessing the profitability of an order in the AHD setting [1].

Existing literature has primarily focused on the single-day delivery problem. Furthermore, all studies addressing the sequential nature of this problem have relied on Value Function Approximation (VFA). [18] suggest an efficient approximation suitable for large-scale applications. They first split the region into smaller independent strips, following [5]’s strategy. Then propose an affine VFA for each of the areas and estimate the parameters offline. Contemporaneously, [8] combine insertion costs with a dynamic variant of seed-based routing approximation in a Mixed-Integer Programming (MIP) model, which they solve to approximate the value function at each state. Since the number of decision variables grows exponentially with the problem’s size, particularly with the number of time windows, the suitability for large-scale online applications is compromised. [9]’s model has a fundamental precondition that the e-grocer knows the spatial (probability) distribution of customers’ locations and respective basket values and feeds a routing algorithm with the already booked customers and a prediction of the incoming customers. Like [18], [9] also learn an affine VFA. However, instead of relying on region segmentation, they suggest a parametrization of the value function with route-based features. They report better results than those achieved by [18]’s approach in their set of instances. In [15], the presented time slots are either categorized as standard or as flexible. The flexible ones have a higher slot size, which is preferable to the retailer but less convenient to the customer. For that reason, a flexible slot is never higher priced than any feasible standard slot. The authors pointed out that it would be desirable to include the choice of slots from adjacent days. As the number of slots increases, a fast online calculation procedure becomes even more important. Our work aims to address both these gaps.

3 PROBLEM DEFINITION

In this section, we elaborate on the formulation of the sequential decision-making problem and provide an explanation of the customer choice model. This model plays a crucial role in understanding how customers respond to variations in the presented price panel.

3.1 MDP formulation

The problem is modeled as a MDP, defining the tuple (S, A, P, R) , where S is the state space (including system and customer-related features), A is the action space (possible price panels to be shown), P is the transition probability function (considering a realistic customer choice model), and R is the reward function (characterizing revenue and delivery costs). The system begins at an initial state s_0 , and a new decision epoch k is triggered whenever a new customer arrives on the online platform, leaving the system at state s_k . This continues until the final state s_K is reached with the arrival of the last customer of the considered booking horizon. In the end, the Multi Period Vehicle Routing Problem with Time Windows (MPVRPTW) is solved [10] for the booked orders, unveiling the total delivery costs.

State: A new state s_k is triggered when a customer arrives on the online platform. It is assumed that the retailer only makes a decision

after the customer has added all products to the basket. The state comprises three components: physical information (e.g., current capacity and already booked customers), customer information (e.g., new customer location and basket value), and belief information (e.g., predicted spatial distribution of upcoming clients and customer choice model).

Action: The action space A_k consists of two steps. First, the retailer blocks unfeasible time slots. This is done by comparing the number of accepted customers in a given time slot with a predefined threshold, as proposed by [19]. If the cutoff time is not respected (e.g., a customer arriving on Tuesday cannot book for Monday), those slots are also blocked. After blocking, a price panel $F_k = [f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n]$ is presented for the available slots, where f_j denotes the delivery fee for each available slot j .

Transition: Given the current state s_k and the correspondent action a_k (presented price panel), the customer chooses a time slot or walks away. The customer's decision is modeled using a choice model that incorporates both a deterministic component and a stochastic component. The next state s_{k+1} is triggered when a new customer arrives. Formally, the transition can be represented as

$$s_{k+1} = P(s_k, a_k, o_k) \quad (1)$$

where o_k is the customer's outcome (either a chosen time slot or walkaway).

Reward: The reward R_k at each state is defined as

$$R_k = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if the customer walks away} \\ B_k \cdot \theta + f_k, & \text{if a time slot is selected} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where B_k is the basket value of customer k , θ is the gross profit margin, and f_k is the delivery fee for the selected slot.

In the final state (s_K), the reward is adjusted by applying the discount of the total delivery costs

$$R_K = \begin{cases} -DeliveryCost, & \text{if the customer walks away} \\ B_K \cdot \theta + f_K - DeliveryCost, & \text{if a time slot is selected} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where *DeliveryCost* is the combined cost of mileage (transportation cost) and the fixed cost per vehicle used (fleet cost).

Sources of uncertainty: The uncertainty arises from the location, arrival time, and basket value of upcoming customers, as well as their behavior in response to the presented price panel.

3.2 Customer choice model

In [2], the impact of time slot characteristics on customer choice is studied for the same online retailer we are working with. The time slot characteristics include the slot size, lead time, price, day of the week, and time of the day. Clients tend to value tighter slot sizes, as they can get a more precise delivery time, which is convenient. A shorter lead time (hours between the customer booking and delivery) is also preferred. Regarding price, customers attribute higher value to low-priced time slots. The preferred day of the week is Friday, and the most popular time of the day is early morning and end of the afternoon. The value of time slot j for customer k is modeled as follows

$$U_{kj} = x_{kj}^T \beta + \epsilon_{kj} \quad (4)$$

where x_{kj} represents attributes that vary across time slots and, possibly, across customers. As is common in the discrete choice literature, ϵ_{kj} is drawn from a Type I extreme value distribution and represents factors that are unobservable and independent across time slots and customers. Following this structure and studying the five characteristics mentioned above, Equation 5 represents the value of time slot j for customer k .

$$U_{kj} = \beta_1 PRICE_{kj} + \beta_2 LEADTIME_{kj} + \beta_3 SLOTSIZE_j + \sum_h \beta_h TIME_OF_DAY_{kj}^h + \sum_d \beta_d DAY_OF_WEEK_{kj}^d + \epsilon_{kj} \quad (5)$$

Both the lead time and slot size are expressed in hours. The price is expressed in euros. The time of the day and the day of the week are represented by boolean variables.

Other factors, such as basket size and basket composition, also have an impact on customer value perception [2], but will not be considered in our simulation. As our environment consists of a short-period simulation (three days), it is not relevant to consider customer loyalty, as the terms "order" and "customer" are used interchangeably.

The online retail partner does not store data regarding customers who walk away, as such actions are unusual. The following expression is used to approximate the value of the walkaway option under the fair assumption that customers who spend more money on creating a basket (and consequently more time) are more likely to stay. Therefore, the basket value is inversely proportional to the walkaway value. The value that customer k assigns to the no-purchase option ($j = 0$) is given by

$$U_{k0} = \frac{C}{B_k} + \epsilon_{k0} \quad (6)$$

where C is a constant and B_k is the customer's basket value.

Finally, by employing a Multinomial Logistic Regression (MNL) model, each time slot is assigned a probability of choice. The probability of a given customer selecting time slot j is given by Equation 7, where J represents the set of options (including all available slots and the walkaway option) and U_j is the utility that the customer assigns to option j [13].

$$\pi_j = \frac{e^{U_j}}{1 + \sum_{i \in J} e^{U_i}}, \quad \forall j \in J, \quad (7)$$

4 PANEL SELECTION FRAMEWORK

Our solution approach aims to present the best price panel for each state. The panel creation and selection method is fully described in Figure 1. Firstly, a balanced price panel is defined (step 1), using the known customer choice model with the goal of having higher prices for the most attractive slots, and vice-versa. Then, variations of this panel are created with price incentives for the slots of a given shift (step 2), leading to a discrete set of price panels. As a new customer arrives, a GP-generated mathematical expression is used to calculate the score of each panel out of the previously

Figure 1 – Price panel selection framework.

defined discrete set of panels (step 3). Finally, the highest-scored price panel is presented to the customer (step 4).

The overall tendency of having higher prices for the most valuable slots is captured in the first step, with the balanced price panel. The variations through price incentives are achieved with the panel selection of the following steps.

4.1 Balanced price panel

The definition of the balanced price panel is done by solving a Least Squares Minimization problem, in which the decision variables are f_j (delivery fee of time slot j) and the objective function is to minimize the sum of squared differences in customer utility across time slots (Equation 8). In other words, the prices are defined in a way that all slots have a similar value perception for the customer, with the least attractive slots being compensated with lower prices and vice-versa. This optimization problem is constrained by the retailer’s request of having minimum (a) and maximum (b) values for the fees (Equation 9). The limitation on the maximum price difference between time slots is viewed by the company as a way to gently introduce dynamic pricing without overwhelming or shocking the customer. In the numerical experiments presented in Section 6, the delivery fees of the balanced price panel range from 5.99 € to 7.99 €.

$$\min \sum_{j \in J} \left(U_j - \frac{1}{|J|} \sum_{j \in J} U_j \right)^2 \quad (8)$$

$$a \leq f_j \leq b \quad (9)$$

Lead time is a variable that changes based on the arrival time of each customer. Therefore, we will focus only on static variables to develop a static balanced panel (slot size, time of the day, and day of the week).

It is relevant to note that only deterministic factors are used for the development of this model. When confronted with a panel, the customer’s value perception depends both on deterministic and stochastic elements, as explained in the previous section.

4.2 Discrete set of price panels

After the balanced price panel is created, we generate seven variations of it, resulting in a discrete set of panels.

In Figure 2, an example of a price panel variation is presented. The balanced price panel, which already assigns higher prices to the most valuable time slots, undergoes a uniform discount across all time slots in the Monday morning shift to create the “Cheap Monday Morning” panel. If Monday morning is the best shift to serve the customer, this panel is shown, in order to nudge the customer to select time slots within that shift.

Balanced Price Panel				Cheap Monday Morning			
	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday		Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday
09:00 - 10:00	7.77	7.68	7.61	09:00 - 10:00	6.77	7.68	7.61
10:00 - 11:00	7.77	7.68	7.61	10:00 - 11:00	6.77	7.68	7.61
11:00 - 12:00	6.26	6.18	6.10	11:00 - 12:00	5.26	6.18	6.10
12:00 - 13:00	6.26	6.18	6.10	12:00 - 13:00	5.26	6.18	6.10
13:00 - 14:00	7.20	7.12	7.04	13:00 - 14:00	6.20	7.12	7.04
14:00 - 15:00	7.20	7.12	7.04	14:00 - 15:00	6.20	7.12	7.04
15:00 - 16:00	6.21	6.12	6.05	15:00 - 16:00	6.21	6.12	6.05
16:00 - 17:00	6.21	6.12	6.05	16:00 - 17:00	6.21	6.12	6.05
17:00 - 18:00	7.51	7.43	7.35	17:00 - 18:00	7.51	7.43	7.35
18:00 - 19:00	7.51	7.43	7.35	18:00 - 19:00	7.51	7.43	7.35
19:00 - 20:00	7.56	7.47	7.40	19:00 - 20:00	7.56	7.47	7.40
20:00 - 21:00	7.56	7.47	7.40	20:00 - 21:00	7.56	7.47	7.40

Figure 2 – Price panel variation example.

4.3 Price panel selection

As a new customer arrives, a mathematical expression composed of state features is used to assign a score to each price panel (e.g., Equation 10). The mathematical expression is obtained with GP and has three main benefits in comparison to other approaches: 1) the shape of the formula is non-restricted, allowing the evolutionary algorithm to combine terminals and operators to better capture the value of each price panel; 2) the use of simple mathematical expressions allows for a higher explainability of the developed policy; 3) the expression is easy-to-compute allowing to swiftly define which price panel to show to the customer.

Literature solutions that rely on solving an online pricing problem consist of optimization problems whose complexity increases with the number of time slots. In a multi-period setting, the number of time slots naturally increases, leading to a higher solving time for these approaches. As our approach relies on a simple mathematical expression, the online running time remains negligible with an increase in days and slot options.

$$\text{Score} = \text{BasketValue} - \text{Occupancy} \quad (10)$$

In the example of Equation 10, the score of a price panel increases with the BasketValue, but decreases with the Occupancy (number of booked customers) of that panel’s shift. If the Monday afternoon shift has a low Occupancy in comparison to the other shifts, the “Cheap Monday Afternoon” panel would receive a higher score due to the low value of the terminal Occupancy. Consequently, this expression would result in a policy that tries to nudge customers to shifts with lower Occupancy.

On the other hand, if a customer has a low BasketValue and all shifts already have a high Occupancy, the score can be negative for all panels. If that happens, the best option becomes the “Walk away” panel (Score = 0), resulting in the presentation of an overall expensive price panel, with the goal of nudging the customer to give up purchasing.

5 POLICY LEARNING FRAMEWORK

Defining the set of terminals to feed the model is challenging, as it must contain sufficient information to compute the score of each panel, accounting for both immediate and future rewards. Figure 3 resumes the GP learning framework used to evolve the population of mathematical expressions. The stopping criterion is the number of generations.

Although there are multiple ways to define the operators (e.g., sum, subtraction, division, multiplication, etc.) to be considered in the symbolic expressions, we decided to discuss them with a team of operational managers. These operational managers, despite having a high educational level (bachelor or above), opted for simple operators that they could easily understand in an isolated form. Regarding the terminals’ selection, the same process was followed.

Given the stochastic nature of customers’ location, basket value, and arrival time, and the inherent variability of the MNL customer choice model, the fitness function used in the evolutionary algorithm is based on the average profit over 5 episode replications. The profit calculation for each episode is given by

$$\text{Profit} = \sum_{k \in K} (B_k \cdot \theta + f_k) - \text{DeliveryCost} \quad (11)$$

corresponding to the sum of the basket value (multiplied by the gross profit margin) and delivery fee of all booked customers, discounted by the total delivery cost.

The parameters of the GP algorithm, which were tuned in preliminary experiments, and the utilized set of features and terminals are described in Table 1. We tested different maximum tree depths in order to analyze the trade-off between performance and explainability, as a higher tree depth likely results in longer and more complex expressions.

Table 1 – GP parameters and their descriptions.

GP Parameter	Description
Generations	50
Population size	50
Elitism rate	12%
Replications	5
Minimum tree depth	1
Maximum tree depth	{1,2,3}
Mutation rate	75%
Crossover rate	25%
Operators set	{+, -, ×, /}
Terminal set	{BasketValue AvgDeliveryFee DistToDepot DistToAvgCustomer DistToNearestCustomer DistToFarthestCustomer Occupancy}

The BasketValue, AvgDeliveryFee, and DistToDepot terminals are self-explanatory. Occupancy corresponds to the number of booked customers in a given shift. The DistanceToCustomer terminals (average, nearest, and farthest) correspond to the distance of the current customer to those already booked in the shift under evaluation.

For example, when calculating the score of the panel “Cheap Tuesday Morning”, the DistToAvgCustomer corresponds to the average distance of the current customer to the already booked customers in time slots of the Tuesday morning shift. All distance-based

Figure 3 – GP learning framework.

terminals were multiplied by the cost per km factor, in order to reduce dimensionality problems between terminals. The BasketValue was multiplied by the gross profit margin.

The running time of the evolutionary algorithm depends on the evaluation function that computes the fitness of the individual. On a MacBook Air (M3, 2024) equipped with 16 GB of RAM, each replication (full episode simulation) takes around 6 seconds to run, with the most computationally expensive task being the routing in the final state. As we calculate the fitness as the average profit of 5 replications to account for the stochasticity of the environment, each individual’s evaluation takes around 30 seconds.

6 NUMERICAL EXPERIMENTS

In this section, we analyze and compare various pricing policies across two distinct business settings. Additionally, we examine the fitness evolution over generations and study the trade-off between policy explainability and performance.

6.1 Instance definition

The online retailer we collaborated with offers the AHD service across multiple regions. The business settings, including fleet size limitations, customer arrival rates, and delivery area, vary between regions. We applied the developed framework to define pricing policies for two distinct regions (A and B), and the results produced personalized expressions tailored to each business setting. The key difference between the two regions lies in the fleet size limitation in region B, where the company incurs additional costs if extra trucks are required.

The testing instance captures essential elements of pricing in AHD, including customer location, basket value, and delivery cost drivers, over three consecutive days, divided into 12 non-overlapping one-hour slots each day (see example in Figure 2). Clients are randomly distributed within a squared region measuring 40 km×40 km, with a central depot. The basket value (in euros) follows a log-normal distribution characterized by $\mu = 4.63$ and $\sigma = 0.64$, according to the retailer’s e-commerce data. The customer arrival follows a Poisson distribution with $\lambda = 50$ customers per day. Each vehicle operates at an average speed of 30 km/h and has a maximum capacity of 10 orders. Fleet costs are set at 50 € per truck, along with a transportation cost of 1.09 € per kilometer traveled. In region B,

the fleet is limited to 3 trucks per shift, and any additionally used truck incurs an extra charge of 150 €. In region A, there are no additional costs.

Straight-line distances between nodes are adjusted using a correction factor of 1.5, providing a rough approximation of the typical shortest path distance on the road network [6].

6.2 Expression evolution and interpretation

Figure 4 illustrates the fitness evolution of the best individual of the population across generations for different tree depth limits in regions A and B. As expected, maximum fitness stagnates quicker for lower tree depths, due to the lower expression possibilities.

For region B, populations constrained to tree depths of 1 and 2 achieved the same final fitness. The highest fitness was obtained by the population with a maximum tree depth of 3.

In region A, the highest fitness corresponds to an individual of the population with a maximum tree depth of 2, close to the fitness achieved by the best individual of the population with a maximum tree depth of 3. It is important to emphasize that the tree depth was not strictly enforced but rather limited. This means that solutions generated with a higher depth limit are not required to reach that limit. Allowing for a higher limit enables the evolutionary process to explore a broader search space, potentially leading to diverse solutions. However, this flexibility may not always converge to the best solution within the predefined number of generations.

In theory, higher tree depths can lead to more sophisticated, better-performing individuals. However, a greater depth comes at the cost of producing longer, more challenging-to-read expressions. Operational managers must carefully balance the trade-off between performance and explainability. For these business settings, solutions with a maximum depth of 2 strike the best balance between these two factors.

The mathematical expressions of Equations 12 and 13 represent the best individuals obtained for regions A and B, respectively.

$$\text{Score} = 2 \times \text{BasketValue} - \text{DistToAvgCustomer} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{Score} = \text{BasketValue} - \text{DistToAvgCustomer} + \frac{\text{DistToAvgCustomer} - \text{DistToDepot}}{\text{DistToDepot}} \quad (13)$$

Figure 4 – Maximum fitness across generations for different tree depth limits in regions A and B.

Equation 12 results from the evolution restricted to a maximum tree depth of 2. Consequently, the obtained expression is easy to read and interpret. The score becomes negative only when the basket value is extremely low, and the average distance to customers already booked in the shift is high. Consequently, this policy rarely triggers the display of the “Walk away” panel and aims to nudge the customer toward time slots where the already booked customers are located nearby, leading to space aggregation and savings in delivery costs.

For region B, Equation 13 was obtained. This expression was derived using a maximum tree depth of 3, making it longer and more difficult to interpret. The third element in the expression consists of a division that balances the distance of the customer to the depot and the distance to the already booked customers. Since the evolutionary algorithm does not incorporate weights for the terminals, including the DistanceToDepot in the final parcel helps balance the impact of the DistToAvgCustomer within the expression.

Compared to the one for region A, this expression places less emphasis on basket value and is more likely to produce negative scores, resulting in the more frequent display of the “Walk away” panel. This behavior aligns with the fact that region B has a strict fleet size limit, making it essential for an effective pricing policy to be more selective about which clients to serve. Attempting to serve all clients in region B would increase fleet costs, necessitating a more selective approach.

6.3 Policy definition

For both regions, we compare our solution against benchmark pricing policies, regarding the total profit and other operational metrics. The comparison policies include a Random (RND) policy, which corresponds to a random selection of panels from the discrete set of panels. The Homogeneous Baseline Panel (HBP) represents the currently utilized static policy by the online retail partner, with the same fee for all slots. Additionally, the Balanced Price Panel (BPP) is defined in the first step of our framework, with higher

delivery fees for the most attractive slots. Finally, our proposed policy, termed Genetic Programming Panel (GPP), leverages GP to optimize panel selection.

6.4 Results analysis

The comparison of the policies in regions A and B is presented in the numerical example of Table 2. The results consist of mean values from ten simulations, as they accurately reflect how the policy reacts to the stochasticity of the environment.

The BPP policy outperforms the HBP policy in both regions by effectively reducing fleet costs. This improvement is attributed to the homogenization of value across the price panel, which results in a wider time-wise distribution of customers. In contrast, the HBP policy assigns the same price to all time slots, leading to cannibalization of the most popular slots and an increased likelihood of needing additional trucks (higher fleet cost). The BPP policy is particularly interesting for region B, where the fleet size is limited and it is key to avoid high customer concentration in a reduced number of time slots.

In region B, the GPP policy results in a higher number of customer walkaways (29.30), as an overall expensive price panel is shown when it is not cost-effective to serve the customer in any shift. This policy leads to a higher mean basket value (150.85), retaining a more valuable customer selection. However, in region A, due to the nonexistence of a fleet size limitation, the number of walkways is much lower (5.00), as the policy almost always redirects customers to time slots, rarely presenting the “Walk away” panel.

The profit increase with the GPP policy is not due to the “cherry-picking” of customers close to the depot, as the mean road distance to the depot is similar across all policies. Instead, our policy offers discounts for specific shifts, which leads to a lower mean delivery fee (5.11 in region A and 5.17 in region B). Customers react to the provided incentive, allowing for more efficient operations with a lower number of routes (21.50 in region A and 19.30 in region B), resulting in reduced transportation and fleet costs.

By analyzing Equations 12 and 13, we can conclude that the learned expressions lead to higher scores when the customer is closer to the already booked orders in the shift under evaluation. This way, the GPP policy promotes spatial aggregation, resulting in lower transportation costs. Also, it does not discriminate against customers from a distant location but rather tries to nudge them to a shift in which they will be closer to already booked orders.

The poor performance of the RND policy demonstrates that profit increase is not merely a function of the available discrete set of panels, but rather depends on dynamically selecting the best panel from that set, given the current state.

Figure 5 illustrates the delivery fee for each time slot for a given customer located at a specified distance from the depot. The overall pricing for each time slot remains similar (indicated by the color gradients), with higher costs assigned to the most attractive slots. This is achieved in the first step of our framework when the balanced price panel is generated. However, some discounts or price increases are visible, which indicate adjustments designed to reflect different pricing strategies for certain time slots. Notably, the discounts do not discriminate against customers based on their distance to

Table 2 – Comparison of policy outcomes for regions A and B.

Policy	Mean Reward (€)	Mean Basket (€)	Mean Delivery Fee (€)	Mean Transp Cost (€)	Mean Fleet Cost (€)	Mean Number of Walkaways	Mean Number of Routes	Mean Road Distance to Depot (km)
Region A (unlimited fleet size)								
RND	1900.24	132.20	5.75	1847.07	1180.00	24.40	23.60	19.07
HBP	2467.37	130.59	6.99	2043.61	1415.00	2.60	28.30	19.05
BPP	2886.32	137.61	7.00	2062.72	1340.00	3.90	26.80	18.98
GPP	3307.12	140.55	5.11	1546.39	1075.00	5.00	21.50	19.07
Region B (low fleet size limit)								
RND	1310.24	132.20	5.75	1847.07	1770.00	24.40	23.60	19.07
HBP	1407.37	130.59	6.99	2043.61	2475.00	2.60	28.30	19.05
BPP	1966.32	137.61	7.00	2062.72	2260.00	3.90	26.80	18.98
GPP	2746.91	150.85	5.17	1289.38	1255.00	29.30	19.30	19.04

Figure 5 – Fee value by time slot and distance to depot.

the depot, as all distance levels receive discounts. This, combined with the use of a reduced set of panels that share a similar cost structure, with discounts applied only at the shift level, enhances the likelihood that the developed framework will be accepted by customers.

7 CONCLUSION

In this paper, we introduced a novel approach that leverages GP within a MDP framework to address the dynamic pricing of time slot delivery fees in the context of AHD. The main contributions of this work are threefold.

First, we extended the dynamic time slot pricing problem to the multi-period scenario, as existing literature has predominantly focused on same-day delivery. Additionally, we are the first to incorporate driver shifts into cost calculations.

Second, our method emphasizes transparency and explainability by producing symbolic decision policies that are explainable by design. These policies can be easily interpreted by operational managers, who are actively involved in the expression generation

process. By incorporating human-guided terminal engineering and operator selection, the generated decision policies are more likely to remain transparent and understandable, crucial for real-world deployment and operational managers’ acceptance.

Finally, through computational experiments and analysis, we verified the effectiveness of our approach in maximizing profits. This was achieved by nudging customer behavior with discounts for certain time slots, promoting spatial aggregation, which leads to lower transportation and fleet costs. Our panel selection framework outperformed the benchmark policies across two different settings, reflecting distinct delivery environments representative of two regions where the online retailer operates. By testing different maximum tree depths for the evolutionary algorithm, we explored the trade-off between performance and explainability, derived from the length of the obtained mathematical expressions.

The same framework can be applied to other retailers operating in the AHD setting. However, an empirical study on customer choice preferences is crucial for defining the balanced price panel in the first step of the framework.

The future of our GP approach may entangle additional interactions with operational managers, transforming them into important actors in the evolutionary process of symbolic expressions. Moreover, it is important to explore more advanced GP algorithms with powerful optimization capabilities [16] and interpretability-focused features [7], or even new GP extensions considering constant optimization [17].

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work is financed by National Funds through the Portuguese funding agency, FCT - Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, within project LA/P/0063/2020 (DOI 10.54499/LA/P/0063/2020). Additionally, the research has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 - The EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation 2014-2020, under grant agreements 952060 and 101120406.

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